

WAYS TO IMPROVE MARKETING ACTIVITIES AT "SHAKHRIYOR TOUR SERVIS" LLC

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Abstract. *In this article, the improvement of hospitality services in the field of marketing technologies, the development and prospects of the hospitality industry, development of the marketing complex, expansion of the range of hospitality services and development of additional tourist services.*

Keywords: *tourism, hospitality, marketing, service, assortment, technology,*

INTRODUCTION

Improvement of marketing activity in tourism and development of the service sector is one of the priorities in our country. In our republic, in 2021, the share of this sector in the country's gross domestic product is set to reach 64%.

Tourism and hotel business have a special place in the service sector. Therefore, as the President noted, "It is inevitable that the development of this sector will make a huge contribution to the economic and social development of our country by attracting a lot of foreign tourists to our country, and most importantly, by providing large foreign exchange earnings."

The existence of both the necessity and the opportunities for the tourism and hospitality business, the continuous increase of the requirements for it, imposes the requirements to strengthen the economy and increase the efficiency of the tourist complexes that carry out these types of activities, to organize the management tools that serve this, such as tourism marketing in accordance with today's requirements. This demand, in turn, necessitates deep research of the problems of economic development and efficiency improvement of tourist complexes, as well as theoretical, organizational and methodological issues of marketing in them.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The improvement of hospitality services in the field of marketing technologies is included.

To achieve this result, several tasks were set in the work:

- Development and prospects of the hospitality industry in Uzbekistan.
- Developing a marketing complex in the hospitality industry.
- Expanding the range of hospitality services and development of additional tourist services.
- Analyzing the main directions and results of marketing activities in "Shakhriyor tour servis" LLC;
- Show problems related to marketing activities in "Shakhriyor tour servis" LLC;
- Show ways to improve marketing activities in tourist enterprises.

The main goal of the society is to provide the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a job, satisfy their need for various products and services, as well as get income from entrepreneurship.

In order to achieve its main goal, the society carries out the following types of activities:

- organization of hotels and provision of services,

- travel operator, accepting and sending tourists, organization of travel services,
- buy foreign tourism and national tourism Development of domestic travel routes, organization of excursions, formation and reception of groups of tourists, provision of motor transport, provision of various services to guests,
- opening ticket offices, obtaining, pre-presenting and selling air tickets of the national airline "Uzbekistan Khavo Yullari" and other foreign airlines on the basis of an agency agreement.

It is known that there is a problem of creating all conditions for tourists for new companies to engage in tourist activities. The issue of lodging and feeding tourists will be especially relevant. Therefore, a lot of time and effort was spent on solving organizational problems in 2021. This can be seen from the information on the reception of tourists. (Table 1)

Table -1

Dynamics of reception of tourists by "Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC during 2020-2021

T/R	Indicator name	Unit of measure	2020 year	2021 (1 sq.)	2021 (expected)	change	in % compared to 2020
1	Number of tourists arriving in Kabul	person	172	27	220	+48	127.9
	Including						
2	Foreign countries	person	134	16	160	+26	119.4
3	MDX countries	person	8	1	20	+12	250
4	Uzbekistan	person	30	10	40	+10	133.3

It can be seen that "Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC focused on foreign tourists in its activities. 78% of the received tourists were tourists from foreign countries, 5% were guests from the CIS countries and 17% were citizens of Uzbekistan.

At the same time, in 2021, "Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC is planning to further expand its activities and is thoroughly preparing for the season. According to the plan, it is planned to increase the number of tourists received in 2021 by almost 28%, including the number of foreign tourists by 20%, and the number of Uzbek tourists by 33%. Diagrams 1 and 2.

diagram 1. Results of receiving tourists in 2021 of "Shakhriyor Tur Servis" LLC

Diagram 2. Number of tourist admissions in 2021 at "Shakhriyor Tur Servis" LLC.

Formation of the flow of tourists has a positive effect on the economic indicators of "Shakhriyor tour servis" LLC. (Table 2)

Table-2

Financial and economic indicators of "Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC in 2020-2021

t/r	Indicator name	Unit of measure	2020 year	2021 (1 sq.)	2021 (expected)	change	in % compared to 2020
1	Net income	m. sum	105281.2	16005.6	130416	+25134.8	123.9
	Including						
2	Tourist services	m. sum	41586	7125.2	56861.4	+15275.4	136.7
3	Hotel services	m. sum	46534	6870.4	54122.6	+7588.6	116.3
4	Transport services	m. sum	12212.6	1684.9	12780.8	+568.2	104.6
5	Excursion services	m. sum	4948.6	324.5	6651.2	+1702.6	134.4

According to the data, the total net income in 2020 was 105,281.2 thousand soums. In the first quarter of 2021, it was equal to 16,005.6 thousand soums. Based on the concluded contracts, the net income expected for 2020 is equal to 130,416 thousand soums and is expected to increase by 123.9% compared to 2020. Of course, since the receipts from tourists include all services, there is a need to analyze their sources. If we analyze the composition of the receipts in 2020, tourist services accounted for 39%, services provided by hotels accounted for 44%, and transportation services accounted for 12%. and 5% is the result of excursion services (diagram 3.) So, most of the net income should be transferred to hotels and transport organizations based on the Agreement.

diagram 3. The composition of the net income of "Shakhriyor tour servis" LLC in 2020

In 2021, the activity was extended by "Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC increased attention to increase its share in the structure of income through improvement. As a result, concrete measures have been developed to increase the weight of tourist services. If these measures are effective, the share of tourist services will be increased to 44%, hotel services will be reduced to 41%, and the share of transport services will be reduced to 10%.

diagram 4. The composition of the net income of "Shakhriyor Tur Servis" LLC for 2021

In 2020, the "Shakhriyor Tour Service" tour company paid great attention to the financial result, therefore, according to the results of the year, a net profit of 9924.4 thousand soums was achieved, which is 9.6% of the net income. (table...) This indicator is not bad for tourism companies. However, in 2020, the management of "Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC plans to further increase the profit and it is expected to reach 15,400,000 soums.

Table -3

In 2020-2021, the relative indicators of the "Shakhriyor tour service" tour company per 1 tourist

t/r	Indicator name	Unit of measure	2020 year	2021 (1 sq.)	2021 (expected)	change	in % compared to 2020
1	Net income	M.sum	105281.2	16005.6	130416	+25134.8	123.9
2	Net profit	m. sum	9924.4	1684.8	15400	+5475.6	155.2
3	Net income per 1	M.sum	612.1	592.8	592.8	-19.3	96.8

	tourist						
4	1 net profit per tourist	M.sum	57.7	62.4	70.0	+12.3	121.7

In 2020, the net income per tourist amounted to 612,100 soums, while in 2012 it is expected to be 592,800 soums, that is, it is planned to lower the prices. At the same time, the net profit per tourist in 2020 is equal to 57,700 soums, which is much lower than the average figure.

"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC we believe that the importance of his professional partners is high in his success in the market. As mentioned above, the company has made contracts with a number of companies to increase competitiveness. If we analyze the main tourist services provided at the moment, hotel and catering services are provided by other organizations, because they have much higher capabilities in their field and have many years of experience in providing quality services.

Table-4

Types of services provided to tourists by the "Shakhriyor Tur Servis" tour company

No	Service types	Posted by Kim
1	Registration of documents of accepted tourists	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
2	Organization of individual trips	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
3	Reception of group tourists	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
4	Reception and monitoring of tourists	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
5	Organizing the departure tickets of tourists	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
6	Accommodation of tourists	
7	Organizing meals for tourists	Restaurants "Samarkand", "Standard", "Afrosiab", "Karimbek".
8	Organization of transport services	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
9	Organization of domestic tourism	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
10	Organization of ecotourism	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC
11	Organization of mountain tourism	"Shakhriyor Tour Service" LLC

In order to implement the marketing concept in the tourist enterprise, the relevant marketing service is implemented. In the organizational structure of this type of enterprise, the

marketing service is a link that performs the activities of each department. The main organizational types of the marketing department are:

- functional organization;
- organization according to the product principle;
- organization according to the regional principle.

The functional organization of the marketing department means that the responsibility for solving each issue is attached to a separate person or group:

Figure 3. Functional organization of the marketing department.

The schedule may vary depending on the scope of activity of each tour company. It also depends on the form of the travel agency, or the attention allocated to the marketing department. Some firms have separate advertising and public relations departments.

When organizing a marketing department according to the product principle, the main focus is on offering certain types of products. In this case, each product or set of products has its own manager.

Large travel companies with a wide distribution network often organize marketing services on a regional basis. In doing so, they have functional independence depending on the working conditions in the national and regional market. It should be noted that there is no ideal structure for organizing a marketing service that can be used in any situation. The organizational structures we have presented have their strengths and weaknesses.

A firm to organize a marketing service it is necessary to analyze the performance indicators and choose the main goals.

The analysis of the indicators of the firm's activity is multifaceted, and during this analysis it is necessary to consider many variable indicators. At the same time, it should be emphasized that when assessing each direction of the company's activity, limited criteria - indicators are involved. They represent the set goal and show the contribution of each direction in achieving this set goal.

The level of realization of the set goal, in turn, shows the effectiveness of management, the interest of each employee in the success and, in general, whether the choice of marketing strategy is correct or incorrect.

The goals of any firm (especially a large firm) are very diverse, and they can be graded according to their nature.

When analyzing each major line of a firm's activity, any intended goal for that line of activity is taken into account. The conclusion (result) of the analysis comes from the conclusion

that the result of the activity is being carried out correctly or incorrectly in order to achieve the highest result.

Marketing research scheme.

1-stage. Defining the problems and the purpose of the research

Stage 2. Selection of information sources.

3rd stage. Gathering the necessary information

4th stage. Analysis of collected information

Stage 5. Show results

Any organization strives to achieve its goals. These objectives are the main chapter in the planning of marketing programs. A marketing control system is used to evaluate the work done to achieve the goal. Marketing control is a continuous, continuous review of the marketing process. In other words, it is a comparison of the norm and the real situation. The control process usually consists of 4 stages:

- determination of plan amounts and standards (goals and standards);
- determining the real state of indicators;
- comparison;
- analyze the results.

The main purpose of marketing control is:

- determining the degree of achievement of the goal (deviation analysis);
- determining the possibility of improving conditions (feedback);
- examination of the level of the firm to changes in the environment.

Marketing control also implements special forms of systemic control:

- control of results, control of the implementation of the annual plan, control of income, control of the effectiveness of marketing activities;
- strategic control to verify that the firm is fully utilizing its marketing opportunities.

It is difficult to imagine modern tourism without advertising. It is such a wide and multifaceted activity that it is often separated as a separate direction. However, practice shows that high advertising efficiency can be achieved only with the help of marketing. Advertising is an integral part of marketing communications.

The purpose of advertising:

- organizational activities aimed at attracting consumers and promoting something widely,
- spreading information about something or a person for the purpose of popularity.

Advertising is the most convenient means of providing information to customers in the field of tourism. Based on the behavior of customers, drawing their attention to various services, raising the expectations of the firm, strengthening its position in society is carried out with the help of advertising. Therefore, effective advertising activity is an important tool in achieving the goals of the marketing strategy of the company.

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